

Project website

DELIVERABLE 6.3

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Abstract

Project website

This deliverable report provides a snapshot of the FAIRiCUBE website. This document reflects the state of the FAIRiCUBE website on Friday, 30.09.2022.

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1. Introduction

The dissemination, exploitation, and communication strategy of FAIRiCUBE is meant to maximise the promotion and sharing of results. The overall objective of the strategy will be to increase the visibility of the project and project results by addressing key target groups, the formulation of relevant and targeted messages and the use of up-to-date communication media for reaching out and collecting feedback.

The website is central to the dissemination strategy and communicates information and services from the project. It will act as the gateway to all project results (guidelines, services).

2. Current status website

The website is accessible via fairicube.eu and fairicube.org. The hosting is organised by NILU and Wordpress is used to create content of the website (fairicube.wp.nilu.no). At the moment a simple structure is used to disseminate the information. In future extra pages or features facilitating dissemination actions will be added.

The following pages are operational at the moment:

- Homepage with key information on the objectives and partners (Figure 2-1, Figure 2-2)
- Project page showing more elaborate information on objectives, use cases and the FAIRiCUBE Hub (Figure 2-3)
- Result page showing the milestones and deliverables and in future will link to the published deliverables (Figure 2-4)
- Event page showing passed and upcoming events (Figure 2-5)

Figure 2-1: FAIRiCUBE project website homepage

Figure 2-2: Partner information and Footer of homepage of FAIRiCUBE website

Our mission

The core objective of FAIRiCUBE is to enable players from beyond classic Earth Observation (EO) domains to provide, access, process, and share gridded data and algorithms in a FAIR and TRUSTable manner.

This project's goal is to leverage the power of Machine Learning (ML) operating on multi-thematic datacubes for a broader range of governance and research institutions from diverse fields, who at present cannot easily access and utilize these potent resources. Selected use cases will illustrate how data-driven projects can benefit from cube formats, infrastructure, and computational benefits. They will guide us in creating a user-friendly FAIRiCUBE HUB, which is tightly integrated to the common European data spaces. The FAIRiCUBE HUB will provide relevant stakeholders an overview of both data and processing modules readily available to be applied to these data sources. The HUB will support users not intimately familiar with the worlds of Earth observation and machine learning to scope the requirements and costs of their desired analyses. In this way the HUB will contribute to uptake of these resources by a broader community. The FAIR sharing of results with the community will be fostered by providing easy to use tools and workflows directly in the FAIRiCUBE HUB.

Figure 2-3: FAIRiCUBE project website project page

Deliverables

Deliverable	Deliverable name	Work package number	Short name of lead participant	Type	Dissemination level	Delivery date (in months)
D1.1	Consortium agreement	1	NIL	R	CO	M1
D1.2	1 st year progress report	1	NIL	R	PU	M12
D1.3	2 nd year progress report	1	NIL	R	PU	M24
D1.4	3 rd year progress report	1	NIL	R	PU	M36
D1.5	Project handbook	1	NIL	R	CO	M4
D1.6	Validation report	1	4SF	R	PU	M24, M36
D2.1	UC Progress report	2	4SF	R	PU	M12, M24, M36
D2.2	Report on UC data source synergies	2	4SF	R	PU	M6, M24
D2.3	UC Analysis Plans	2	4SF	R	PU	M6, M12, M18, M30
D2.4	UC Ingest/Process synergy report	2	4SF	R	PU	M12, M24
D2.5	Workshop presentations and minutes	2	4SF	R	PU	M24, M36
D2.6	Validation of UC	2	S4E	R	PU	M24, M36

Figure 2-4: FAIRiCUBE project website result page with list of deliverables

Figure 2-5: FAIRiCUBE project website event page with list of passed and upcoming events

3. Website management and further development

A number of project members have rights to add content to the website. Wordpress is used, which is fairly easy to use. News items, events etc. can easily be added. More structural changes such as adding an extra page or feature for dissemination actions can easily be done as well. That makes the website very flexible, and it can be quickly adjusted to the needs. The website will be updated at least monthly, but, if necessary, in between updates will be carried out.